

DEVELOPMENT OF INTEGRATED SYSTEMS FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING AND EARTHQUAKE RISK MANAGEMENT IN HISTORIC STRUCTURES: STORM APPROACH

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Summary : In the earthquake risk mitigation strategy of buildings, it is aimed to estimate the weaknesses of structures and to take engineering measures against these weaknesses (such as stabilization, strengthening or retrofitting) in order to improve structural performance towards earthquakes. Therefore, it is one of the crucial targets of performance evaluation and risk assessment strategies in structural engineering and it is widely achieved by developing fragility and/or capacity curves using analytical models of structures. However, the earthquake risk mitigation strategy in historical structures are strictly limited by provisions related to the protecting of CH (ICOMOS 2003 and ICCROM 1998). Thus, in the disaster risk management of historical buildings, it is necessary to carry out interdisciplinary studies not only to include engineering aspect, but also architectural conservation, restoration and first aid concerns as well. The H2020 STORM project, which is being implemented in this context, aims to develop an integrated platform for the monitoring and control of environmental and human-induced risks of historical structures at pilot sites in Europe. Ephesus amphitheater was chosen as the pilot site in Turkey.

The integrated earthquake risk module of STORM consists of two sources of information, namely: engineering (pre-earthquake) and operational (post-earthquake). Before the

earthquake, a numerical simulation is performed by generating the Finite Element Model (FEM) of the structure. A three dimensional (3D) numerical model will help visualize the behavior of the structure under seismic effects. The structure will then be analyzed using the FEM model in order to detect damage mechanisms for the entire structure and its vulnerability to seismic forces. A risk measure (engineering demand parameter: EDP) will be defined to indicate the damage state of the structure. It will be linked to three main objectives, namely, aesthetics, architectonic and structural. Each objective will then be subdivided into three different performance levels. In other words, the structural damage states will be transformed into meaningful information to provide first aid for different disciplines.

In the second part, a health monitoring system will be developed for the structure. The structural health monitoring system is a quick and effective method for structural identification and assessment of the current state of the structures after an earthquake. The earthquake module will process the actual data coming from the site after the earthquake and compare it with the threshold values in question and provide preliminary information about whether the damage in the structure is cosmetic, architectural or structural or their combination. In this way, the authority would determine if it is okay to enter and use the structure, damage to frescoes or requirements for restoration in the next few minutes after the earthquake and the authorities will be informed via short message. This will help activate emergency scenarios, define triage, and effective use of personnel after a disaster. This approach is related to the “first aid” response for humans, structure and restoration purposes. Because the platform will have a flexible architecture, it is expected to update the system by the addition of new structures to be analyzed

Key Words : STORM Project, Ephesus Ancient Theatre, Disaster and Risk management, Point Cloud Data, Finite Element Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The protection of European Cultural Heritage is of the top priority for policy makers, the institutions in charge of protecting those, tourists, and educators at local and national levels as well. Europe's cultural heritage is being lost at an alarming rate, not only due to natural decay and human impacts but frequently also as a result of environmental changes, climatic conditions or natural hazards.

Historical structures showing aspects of high architectural interest are identified as cultural assets that should be preserved for posterity. Over time, some of these structures have disappeared while some have been preserved to this day. However, they have been subjected to structural deterioration during their lifetime for several reasons. It is a well-known fact that seismic forces may cause considerable damage to architectural heritage, but may also inflict losses in terms of historical, cultural, and architectural values. Seismic effects are the most important risk factors that threaten structural safety of structures. In fact, the seismic resistance of a structure depends on its geometrical configuration, structural materials and properties, interaction between structural elements, workmanship, and dynamic performance. Architects and structural engineers involved in the rehabilitation and maintenance issues need to adequately recognize structural performance of historical structures so that they could be able to generate compatible solutions in terms of original structural properties. They are mainly faced with the lack of significant information about structural analyses of historical structures, such as load bearing limitations and structural behavior under seismic load. Therefore, earthquake risk mitigation has become an increasingly important topic in recent years.

The STORM earthquake risk module makes use of mainly two sources of information, pre-earthquake engineering and post-earthquake-operational. Before the earthquake, the numerical model of the structure is developed to determine the performance-based building damage threshold levels of the structure. For this purpose, three main performance criteria are

considered, namely, artistic, architectural and structural. For the post-earthquake respond, a structural health monitoring system is constructed. In case of an earthquake, the system will automatically collect and process the actual data coming from the site and compare it with the threshold value of the Engineering Demand Parameter (EDP) in question and provide preliminary information about the extent of the damage in the CH structure. In this way, the authority would be able to determine if it is okay to enter and use the structure as well as the possible damage to the architectonic and artistic features will be analyzed in the next few seconds and sent to authorities by an SMS message. The platform will also provide a resilient communication to ensure that the acquired data is safely transferred from the source to the user during and after disasters. The system architecture of the STORM platform will be flexible so that it can be updated under the light of new information and data for new sites. Therefore, it will be particularly useful for the quick damage assessment and emergency response of CH structures and determination of triage especially in geographically dispersed sites after an earthquake.

The earthquake hazard constitutes the major risk for the CH structures in Europe, particularly in Turkey. Earthquake damage results in loss and the likelihood of sustaining a loss is termed risk. Loss can take many forms, for historical structures it is the loss of CH. Therefore proper recommendations are desirable and necessary to both ensure rational methods of analysis and repair methods appropriate to the cultural context.

The earthquake risk strategy for CH aims to develop a structure specific risk strategy to improve risk preparedness (ICCROM 1998). The structures of architectural heritage present a number of challenges in diagnosis and restoration that limit the application of modern legal codes and building standards. ICOMOS, 2003 indicates that no action should be undertaken without having ascertained the achievable benefit and harm to the architectural heritage, except in cases where urgent safeguard measures are necessary to avoid the imminent collapse of the structures (e.g. after seismic damages); those urgent measures, however, should when possible avoid modifying the fabric in an irreversible way. Preservation principles for seismic retrofit projects indicates that historic materials should be preserved and retained to the greatest extent possible and not replaced wholesale in the process of seismic strengthening. New seismic retrofit systems, whether hidden or exposed, should respect the character and integrity of the historic building and be visually compatible with it in design; Seismic work should be "reversible" to the greatest extent possible to allow removal for future use of improved systems and traditional repair of remaining historic materials. Considering all these restrictions and the huge amount of CH structures to be retrofitted, it is obvious that most CH structures will remain vulnerable to earthquakes. Therefore, it is important that the disaster risk management strategy for CH structures should not only address the long term engineering (retrofitting and strengthening) but also the short term operational aspects, such as stabilization, preservation, conservation and first aid. Such measures aim to preserve the CH structure in its current form.

In the last four decades, many studies and research have carried out works on preventive strategies aimed at protecting the EU cultural buildings and sites (English Heritage, 1998; EMERICI, 2006; PROHITEC, 2008); PERPETUATE, 2012). Although different in their nature and specific objectives, all these projects had prevention and public policies at their core and where (unstructured) support is given by existing disaster procedures.

The risk objectives of the STORM project are selected as defined by PERPETUATE, 2012 in which three risk objectives are defined. Artistic Damage to fresques, mosaics and etc. Architectonic (Restorable damage) Architects, restorers, Human safety Heavy damage/collapse. Performance levels for each type of risk objective needed to define based on detailed engineering analyses. STORM in this aspect provides an integrated solution for the recovery and respond of CH by performing structural health monitoring, quick damage assessment (QDA) and warning messages to activate the first aid.

2. EPHEBUS GREAT THEATRE

The Ancient City of Ephesus is a historical complex which consists of many historical structures such as theatres (small and large), Celsus Library, churches and etc. It is located in the Selcuk district of İzmir province (Figure 1). The site is under the responsibility of the Directorate of Ephesus Museum, a peripheral body of the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism (KVMGM) and classified as UNESCO World Heritage.

Ephesus Great Theatre is the biggest structure in the ancient city of Ephesus. This open-air theatre was initially used for drama, but during later Roman times gladiatorial combats were also held on its stage. Historical records indicate that the theatre had a seating capacity of 20-25,000. The cavea (seats) has sixty six rows of seats, divided by two diazoma (walkway between seats) into three horizontal sections.

The integrity of the Ephesus Great theatre remains is relatively high. It is the largest and best preserved ancient building in Ephesus (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Ephesus pilot site and other archeological sites in Western Anatolia (Google Maps)

Figure 2. Ephesus Great Theatre

During the course of time, Ephesus Great Theatre has suffered some damage and been subject to the risk of collapse due to the natural disasters or human interventions. The skene, especially, has been substantially deformed in terms of its structural integrity and stability. As the northern entrance of the cavea remains unsupported due to the collapse of the stage by time the structural stability of the section of the theater needs to be investigated.

The structure has been renovated several times by using different materials. During the structure's life, construction materials have been deteriorated and have lost their qualities due to many reasons such as environmental conditions and natural disasters.

Damage has been observed on the structure as cracks, fractures, fissures, degradations, separation and decay of structural materials. In fact, structural damages may occur due to several factors such as the soil settlement, temperature variations, excessive loads, and seismic effects. The northern and southern parts of the cavea partially collapsed while the scene section totally collapsed. Various separations have been appeared between structural materials in the entrance section. Spalling and flaking have also been visible in the springing and the voussoirs of parados sections. Additional structural cracks and fractures have been observed at the facades and on top of the structure. The mortar between rubble stone units was partially eroded. The loss of this binding material caused the decrease of structural resistance of the walls (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Some structural damages and deteriorations observed in Ephesus Ancient Theatre

3. HAZARD ASSESSMENT

Risk assessment procedure that has been envisaged in the lights of the current risk assessment standards and guidelines is comprised of following components: identification and analysis of natural hazards and climate change threats; assessing the value of heritage properties exposed to the hazards; analyzing the vulnerability of the heritage properties to the identified hazards; and identifying and analyzing the risks. Five primary natural hazards and threats have been identified for Ephesus Great Theatre based on available literature as well as climate projection and analyses that have been performed within the project. Hazards/threats with high level of significance (As Low As Reasonably Practicable (ALARP) Principle, AEMC 2015, 39) are (1) earthquake (2) wildfire and with medium level of significance (3) cold waves/ heat waves (4)

landslides (5) biological infestation. Exceptional level of value of the Ephesus Great theatre has been portrayed one more time in following exposure assessment component. Present paper focuses on the seismic hazard and reduction of earthquake loss.

3.1. Quick Damage Assessment

Quick Damage Assessment is required for the emergency response in the aftermath of an earthquake. It is aimed to provide short information to site people about the extent of damage at geographically dispersed structures within a couple of minutes after the earthquake. Therefore can be important for the site managers for triage to activate proper emergency response teams such as to save human life, artistic, architectonic features or other valuables at distant sites.

Immediately after the earthquake, it is necessary to know the “extent of damage” and “who will do what?” for the emergency response at a site. Quick Damage Assessment provides such operational information to CH administrators and public authorities for the determination of triage at geographically dispersed sites within a few minutes of the earthquake. By this way, appropriate earthquake mitigation strategies which are consistent with the predefined risk objectives can be applied. The first step for this procedure is to perform a structure specific analyses based on performance based assessment of the CH structure.

4. PERFORMANCE BASED ASSESSMENT OF HISTORICAL STRUCTURES

Performance based assessment (PBA) is a new stream line of research on heritage buildings to assess the performance of historical structures (including mosques, churches, monuments, towers, aqua structures, etc. Evaluation of seismic performance for existing historical structures has been mentioned in many standards (ASCE 41, 2006; EC8-3, 2005). Seismic evaluation of these structures is usually carried out by linear or nonlinear procedures. ASCE 41 (2006) is applicable to all types of buildings and structural materials (concrete, steel or masonry) for seismic rehabilitation, i.e. it is not solely intended to be used for historical structures. ASCE 41 (2006) requires each structural component to be classified as primary or secondary prior to selecting component acceptance criteria, whereas for the analyses, the members are classified as either having force-controlled or deformation-controlled failure modes. The acceptance criteria are defined in terms of drift ratio corresponding to a predefined performance level. EC8-3 (2005) is mainly intended to provide seismic evaluation procedures for existing buildings and for the design of retrofitting projects from conceptual design to structural analysis.

A recently completed European Research Project, PERPETUATE (2012) has developed detailed guidelines on how to seismically assess heritage buildings based on performance-based evaluation principles by considering a structural classification. It has been specifically developed for seismic evaluation and retrofitting of cultural heritage buildings using the performance-based assessment methodology as proposed in both ASCE 41 (2006) and EC8-3 (2005). PERPETUATE (2012) requires a nonlinear static analysis resulting in a pushover curve (base shear vs. lateral displacement curve) on which four damage levels are defined, namely, slight damage (SD), moderate damage (MD), heavy damage (HD), and complete damage (CD). Modeling and verification requires PBA of the structure. PBA suggests pushover analysis be used until a target displacement is reached according to the selected performance level (PL). Engineering demand parameter is the lateral displacement for pushover analysis. When nonlinear dynamic analyses are used, incremental dynamic analysis curve corresponding to lateral force is plotted against the lateral displacement. Incremental dynamic analysis is carried

out scaling peak ground acceleration of the selected strong earthquake ground motions records. PLs are classified into three different groups; namely, use and human life, building conservation and artistic assets conservation. The seismic performance of the heritage building is then defined from high performance level to low performance level as operational, immediate occupancy and life safety for use and human life PL; no damage, damage limitation, significant but restorable damage and near collapse for building conservation PL; near integrity, damaged but with low aesthetic impact, severely damaged but still restorable, loss prevention for artistic assets PL. Definition of Performance Levels on the Capacity Curve, PERPETUATE Figure 4.

Figure 4. Definition of Performance Levels on the Capacity Curve for structures having structural integrity and structural frames in the PERPETUATE project

The seismic risk assessment has to cover a large spectrum from material understanding to PBD and should not result in lack of focus on some of essential issues. Performance levels defined in the PERPETUATE project.

Artistic Assess: Irreparable damage to artistic assets can occur also in the case of moderate damage to structural elements

Conservation: the possibility of restoration, due to the intangible value of a cultural heritage asset

Human Life: the possibility of an immediate occupancy after an earthquake and the preservation of human life are of fundamental importance for a cultural heritage asset

The seismic risk assessment has to cover a large spectrum from material understanding to PBD and should not result in lack of focus on some of essential issues.

Material properties: Determine the behavior of unreinforced masonry

Numerical model: Simulate the structure based on the accurate numerical tools

Numerical analysis: Incremental dynamic analysis under gradually increasing earthquake intensity.

Make decision: Determine the spectral accelerations, displacement and drift ratio corresponding to the selected performance levels. Representative values for two different acceptance criteria are provided in Table 1 for a framed structure and group of stone blocks. The engineering demand parameter for these different types of structures will be different (story drift and spectral acceleration).

Table 1. Representative values for acceptance criteria for drift and acceleration based performance levels

Performance Types	Performance Levels	Acceptance Criteria in terms of drift ratio (%)*	Acceptance criteria in terms of Sa (%g)-
Use and Human Life	Operational	0.05	0.01
	Immediate Occupancy	0.10	0.05
	Life Safety	0.30	0.10
Building Conservation	No Damage	0.10	0.01
	Damage Limitation	0.15	0.10
	Significant but Restorable Damage	0.40	0.20
Artistic Asset	Near Integrity	0.01	None
	Restorable Damage	0.03	None
	Loss Prevention	0.25	None

The vulnerability is assessed based on how many performance levels are exceeded. The following categories are defined:

- a. *Very low (three or less performance levels are exceeded)*
- b. *Low (Four or five performance levels are exceeded)*
- c. *High (Six or seven performance levels are exceeded)*
- d. *Very High (Eight or Nine performance levels are exceeded)*

This ratio will be estimated as soon as acceleration data from the site is received and plotted on the capacity curve. Next step is to apply seismic data collection.

6. NUMERICAL MODELING

The determination of the seismic behavior of historical structures is difficult to obtain by the use of common engineering methods. Masonry structures are composed of sub units that have different shapes and materials, which have different properties. Thus, numerical modelling is the most preferred method for masonry structures. In order to solve the engineering problems

correctly, it is essential that the numerical model is established correctly. There are several different modeling approaches used today for this purpose (Figure 7).

Figure 5. Different modelling techniques for masonry structures

In this study, three-dimensional (3-D) FE models have been developed based on macro modelling techniques. FE analyses program, ANSYS Workbench, has been used to analyze the north side of the theatre with SOLID186 elements, which has 20 nodes and three degrees of freedom per node. A ground motion data recorded the strongest earthquakes in Ephesus was taken into consideration and the dynamic analysis was performed on the numerical model.

7. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF EPHEBUS GREAT THEATRE

7.1. Seismic Data Collection

The seismic toolset consists a three component seismic sensor (GeoSIG force balance accelerometer), 24 bit A/D converter, a modem, a GPS for synchronizing and a dedicated GSM line for online transfer of the acquired data. The seismological data have been collected at the ground and top levels (Figure 5). A specially developed data acquisition interface software is used for the pre-processing and online monitoring the seismic data. A snap shot of the acquired data and their location are shown in Figure 6.

Since the installation of seismic stations (21th April, 2017), about 50 seismic events with magnitudes $3 \geq M \leq 6$ have been recorded. The earthquake response spectra of the recorded ground motions have been calculated and used for the numerical simulation of the structural response.

Initially, the numerical model of the Ephesus Theatre has been generated to predict the response of the structure to recorded ground motions. The material and geometric properties of the structure will be determined and updated considering the data provided from the geophysical measurements. The acquired seismic data will then be used as an input motion to estimate the

response of the structure its vulnerable parts (side walls). In addition, the seismic data can be used to understand the damage mechanisms of the structure, early detection of structural damage and to warn the local authorities about the extent of the damage to help develop proper disaster management and planning procedures.

The epicentral locations of the nearby events and recorded seismic data at Ephesus. Figure 6 shows the earthquake data recorded during the M=4.2 event in Kuşadası. M=6.2 event in Izmir, 12.06.2017. After setting up the seismic station a number of seismic events with magnitudes varying between $3 \leq M \leq 6.2$ have been recorded. An example of the online seismic data (seismic noise) provided from the Ephesus station. The epicentral locations of the nearby events and recorded seismic data at Ephesus. Figure 6 shows the earthquake data recorded during the M=4.2 event in Kuşadası. M=6.2 event in Izmir, 12.06.2017.

Figure 6. Structural Monitoring for Ephesus Pilot Site

Figure 7. An example of the online seismic data (seismic noise) provided from the Ephesus station

7.2 Laser Scanning and Computational Modelling

It is important to understand the structural behavior of historical structures and evaluate their performance for the development of prevention and intervention techniques. The simplest solution for determining the structural behavior is to use computer models and numerical analyses. However, the preparation of the most convenient computational model of the structure has always been challenging.

Numerical models are expected to accurately reflect the real structure in order to obtain realistic numerical results. The laser scanning is very useful tool for developing the three-dimensional (3D) models of structures when there is no design drawings or structural integrity.

The accuracy of the three-dimensional (3D) models of structures is ensured by the use of high definition laser scanning (HDS) technology. This technology can provide an effective and economical solution for 3D modelling from small to large structures with different geometrical configurations and complexities. The laser scanning technology is extensively merging into many fields. The technology enables users to capture many points from the subject structure with high accuracy. In particular, the HDS technology provides both qualitative and quantitative information about a complex object which is discretized as a cloud of millions or billions of points in space. The as-found geometry of Ephesus Great Theatre was captured by means of the HDS using the laser point stations (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Point Cloud Data of Ephesus Great Theatre, north and south sides of the Theatre

7.3. Noise Reduction Process for Point Cloud Data

Noise can be described as the unwanted and unpleasant points on the PC data. These unwanted points can cause errors during analysis when it is too loud. For this reason, the noises must first be removed or reduced from the PC data. In this study, the noise control system was used to eliminate the unwanted and desired points. After the PC was picked up, the inaccurate points such as visitors, trees, birds and plants defined as noise were removed and a filtered PC data was generated (Figure 9).

Figure 9. (a) Figure Meshed model of the structure, (b) Solid Model of the North Side, (c) Smothened Numerical Model of the North Side

Looking at the structural model in Figure 10, one does not expect a characteristic behavior for structural vibrations. Therefore, the peak structural acceleration is considered as the EDP for the structure instead of drift ratio. For the calibration of the numerical model the response of the structure to real events were compared. The system architecture of the BU seismic sensing infrastructure of the Storm Platform a dashboard is developed for this purpose. Resilient communication service of STORM platform is provided in Figure11.

Figure 10. Acceleration records of the earthquake at Ephesus Station

Figure 11. Resilient communication service of STORM platform

8. CONCLUSION

The integrated earthquake risk module of STORM project consists of two sources of information, namely: engineering (pre-earthquake) and operational (post-earthquake). Before the earthquake, numerical simulation is performed by generating the FEM of the structure. A three dimensional (3D) numerical model was generated to visualize the behavior of the structure under seismic effects and the structure was then analyzed by the FEM model in order to determine the damage mechanisms for whole structure and its vulnerability to seismic forces. In the second part, a structural health monitoring system was developed and seismic data was collected from the site. Then, the performance levels of the structure was linked to three main objectives, namely, aesthetics, architectonic and structural and each objective was then subdivided into three different performance levels. In other words, the structural damage states was transformed into meaningful information to provide first aid in different disciplines.

In the future studies, it will be focused on the earthquake module. This module will process the online earthquake signal and compare it with the threshold values in question and provide preliminary information about whether the damage in the structure is cosmetic, architectural, and structural or their combination. In this way, the authority will be able to determine whether it is safe to enter/use the structure and the extent of the damage. This will help activate emergency scenarios, define triage, and effective use of personnel after a disaster. Therefore, it

could be of particular importance to site people who are in charge of geographically dispersed CH structures. This approach is related to the “first aid” response for personnel, structure and restoration purposes. As the platform will have a flexible architecture, it is expected to update the system by the addition of new structures to be analyzed.

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